

HYDROLOGICAL AND GEOGRAPHIC DESCRIPTION AND PLANT BIODIVERSITY OF THE OHANGARON RIVER BASIN

N.N. Oblomurodov¹, S.A. Turdiev²

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, Tashkent State Agrarian University, Tashkent¹

Doctor of Agricultural Sciences, Professor, Tashkent State Agrarian University, Tashkent²

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16990951>

Abstract. The article discusses the geographical location of the Ohangaron river basin, the direction of water flow from a hydrological perspective, and the amount of precipitation during the season. Additionally, based on observations of natural and cultivated plants in the mountainous and foothill areas of the region, their biodiversity and scientific classification are analyzed. The article also highlights the role of trees and shrubs in greening residential areas and their importance in maintaining microclimatic balance.

Keywords: high peak, Chatkal mountain range, Ohangaron river, length 236 km, important for irrigation, walnut groves, wild rose, honeysuckle.

Introduction

It is known that the regions of our Republic are characterized by specific geographical locations, soil types, and climatic conditions. Based on this, studying the sustainability of plant biodiversity, preserving the region's ecological balance, and expanding green areas are among the priority tasks of today. Preventing the loss and reduction of limited biological resources in the regions is a crucial responsibility for all of us. In terms of plant distribution, it is important to thoroughly study the biodiversity of local flora, including trees and shrubs, compile inventories, and comparatively analyze their biomorphological indicators.

In this regard, the forest flora (tree and shrub species) of the Ohangaron River basin, located in the Western Tien Shan mountainous and foothill region, was studied in terms of biological diversity, natural regeneration, and growth development. The Tien Shan mountains cover the western foothill plains and mountainous parts, with altitudes ranging from 300–400 meters up to 4000 meters above sea level.

Figure -1. Geographical location of the Ohangaron river basin

The Ohangaron River basin is situated between the Chatkal and Qurama mountain ranges of the Tien Shan system, extending from the northeast to the southwest. The western part of the

basin opens into the Syrdarya valley, while the upper part consists of deep and narrow rocky gorges known as the Angren Plateau ([source](#)).

The territory of the Ohangaron River basin also adjoins the foothills of the Western Tien Shan. It is open in the north and northwest and bordered by mountains in the southeast. Therefore, the mountainous area of the region receives more precipitation compared to other mountainous and foothill areas of Uzbekistan. The amount of rainfall increases from southwest (250–300 mm) to east (up to 800–900 mm). The Qurama mountain range of the Western Tien Shan, at elevations between 1000 and 3000 meters above sea level, is primarily covered with juniper forests, hawthorn, maple, walnut, wild apple, rosehip, barberry, and other forest plants.

The Ohangaron river basin lies within the Tashkent oasis, bordered by the Ugam and other mountain ranges in the northwest. These surrounding ranges—Ugam, Piskom, and Talas—reach elevations of 3000 to 4000 meters.

The basin of the Ohangaron River occupies the main part of the Western Tien Shan. The Qurama range is distinct from the other mountain systems of the Western Tien Shan. To the southwest of the Chatkal Range lies the high Angren Plateau. The Chatkal Range is one of the largest mountain systems in the Western Tien Shan, with peaks over 4000 meters located in neighboring Kyrgyzstan. The highest point within Uzbekistan is the Greater Chimgan peak, standing at 3309 meters. The highest peak of the Qurama range is Boboiob, reaching 3769 meters.

The Ohangaron River originates from numerous streams formed on the southern slopes of the Chatkal range and the northwestern slopes of the Qurama range. In many places, the riverbed has a canyon shape, and the flow velocity can reach up to 4 m/s. The river valley later widens from 20 meters to 500–600 meters and flows along a terrace-divided small valley until it reaches the Ohangaron reservoir.

During periods of spring precipitation and snowmelt, the water level rises sharply, and the river may split into several branches in wider sections. The average amplitude of water level fluctuations is about 2 meters. After leaving the Ohangaron reservoir, the river flows into a wide valley through a special hydrotechnical channel near the village of Obliq.

The river is fed mainly by snow and glacier waters. Its water level rises twice a year: first during March–April due to intensive snowmelt and frequent precipitation, and second in June–July due to accelerated glacial melt.

The Ohangaron River, a right tributary of the Syrdarya, has a length of 236 km and a drainage basin of 5262 km². It plays a crucial role in irrigating agricultural lands in the Tashkent region. Additionally, the river is a vital water resource for the population and industries of major cities along its course (Angren, Nurabad, Ohangaron and Almalyk).

According to A.K. Nurkhojaev, the Tien Shan mountain system in Uzbekistan is divided into Central and Southern Tien Shan. The Central Tien Shan (Chatkal-Qurama system) includes the Maydntol, Pskom, Ugam, and Korjantau ranges. The Southern Tien Shan includes the Zarafshan, Turkestan, Nurata, Central Kyzylkum, Zirabulok, Qoratepa, and Hisor mountain branches [1].

The Ohangaron river basin covers much of the Western Tien Shan mountain direction.

The average annual temperature of the Ohangaron river basin ranges from 12.5°C to 13.6°C. The number of days with temperatures above +10°C ranges from 211 to 217, and the sum of active temperatures above +10°C is about 2138–2150. The region is dominated by gray soils, meadow soils, and swampy meadow soils [2].

The Angren Plateau consists of high mountainous areas. According to U. Tojiev, Kh. Namazov, Sh. Nafetdinov and K. Umarov, the chemical composition of dark brown meadow-steppe soils of the highlands is as follows (Table 1) [4]:

Table-1

Chemical composition of dark brown meadow-steppe soils in high mountain areas

Layer	Depth, cm	Humus, %	Nitrogen, %	C:N	P ₂ O ₅ , %	K ₂ O, %	CO ₂ Carbonates, %	pH
A ₁	0–8	5,31	0,354	8,7	0,244	2,63	0,33	5,8
A ₂	8–27	3,63	0,245	8,6	0,254	2,67	0,20	6,0
B ₁	27–45	1,35	0,085	9,2	0,146	2,36	0,25	6,1
C ₁	45–65	0,08	0,051	9,1	0,090	2,46	0,17	6,6
C ₂	65–110	0,03	0,018	10,4	0,042	2,58	0,55	6,8
D ₁	110–185	0,02	0,010	1,2	0,078	2,31	0,63	6,8
D ₂	185–230	0,02	0,006	2,0	0,095	2,35	0,80	6,8

The climate of the Ohangaron River region is characterized by high variability. Therefore, fluctuations in air temperature significantly affect the plant population. From the perspective of flora distribution, one can observe the natural populations of needle-leaved and broad-leaved plants, juniper forests, wild fruit plants, walnut groves, hawthorn, maple, rosehip, and willow.

Figure 2. Natural populations of broad-leaved plants

In forest nurseries, fruit and ornamental trees, shrubs, and vines are cultivated with the aim of greening residential areas, creating protective and green belts—i.e., forest melioration. These are grown for both ecological and aesthetic purposes [3].

The seedlings of coniferous and broad-leaved species cultivated in forest nurseries are produced based on scientific and practical methods.

Table-2

Biodiversity of natural and cultivated plants of the mountainous regions of the Ohangaron river basin

№	Uzbek	Latin	Russian	English
1	Qora archa	<i>Juniperus seravcshanika</i>	Можжевельник зеравшанский	Black juniper
2	Грек yong'og'i	<i>Juglans regia</i>	Орех грецкий	Greek Walnut
3	Achchiq bodom	<i>Amugdalu bucharica</i>	Миндал бухарский	Bitter Almond
4	Bodomcha	<i>Amygdalu spinosissima</i>	Миндал колючейший	Little Almond
5	Yovvoyi olma	<i>Malus sieversii</i>	Яблония сиверса	Wild Apple
6	Tog'olcha	<i>Prunus sogdiana</i>	Слива согдийская	<i>Sogdian Plum</i>
7	Sariq do'lana	<i>Crataegus pontica</i>	Боярышник понтийский	Yellow hawthorn
8	Qizil do'lana	<i>Crataegus turkestanica</i>	Боярышник туркестанский	Red hawthorn
9	Oddiy na'matak	<i>Rosa canina</i>	Шиповник обыкновенный	Simple Rose
10	Fedchenko na'matagi	<i>Rosa fedchenkoana</i>	Шиповник Федченко	Rose of Fedchenko
11	Go'zal na'matak	<i>Rosa divina</i>	Шиповник дивная	Beautiful Rose
12	Oqbura na'matagi	<i>Rosa achburensis</i>	Шиповник акбурыйский	Akburian Rose
13	Achison na'matagi	<i>Rosa ecae</i>	Шиповник ачисона	Achison's rose
14	Irg'ay	<i>Cotoneaster</i>	Кизильник	Cotoneaster
15	To'pgulli irg'ay	<i>Cotoneaster racemiflora</i>	Кизильник кистецветный	Ball-flowered cotoneaster
16	Qora mevali irg'ay	<i>Cotoneaster melanocarpa</i>	Кизильник черноплодный	Black fruited cotoneaster
17	Ko'pgulli irg'ay	<i>Cotoneaster multiflora</i>	Кизильник многоцветковый	Multi-flowered cotoneaster
18	Amur uzumi	<i>Vitis amurensis</i>	Виноград амурский	Grape of Amur
19	Bokira uzum	<i>Parthenocissus guinguefolia</i>	Виноград девичий	Virgin Grape
20	Xo'jag'at	<i>Rubus</i>	Ежевика	BlackBerry
21	Maymunjon	<i>Rubus caesius</i>	Ежевика сизая	Gray BlackBerry
22	Yovvoyi uzum	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Виноград винный	Wild Grape
23	Zarang	<i>Acer</i>	Клен	Maple
24	Turkiston zarangi	<i>Acer turkestanicum</i>	Клен туркестанский	Maple of Turkestan
25	Semenov zarangi	<i>Acer Semenovii</i>	Клен семенова	Maple of Semenov

26	Kavkaz qatrang'isi	<i>Celtis caucasica</i>	Каркас кавказский	Frame of Kavkas
27	Turkiston qayini	<i>Betula turkestanica</i>	Бетула Туркестанская	Turkestan boat
28	Tog' jumrut	<i>Rhamnus cathartika</i>	Жестер слабительный	Buckthorn laxative
29	Zirk qoraqand	<i>Berberis oblonga</i>	Барбарис продолговатый	Barberry oblong
30	Tangasimon zirk	<i>Berberis nummularia</i>	Барбарис монетный	Barberry coin
31	Qizil zirk	<i>Berberis integerrima</i>	Барбарис целнокрайный	Red Barberry
32	Shilvi, uchqat	<i>Lonicera tatarica</i>	Жимолость татарская	Tatar honeysuckle
33	Qirq bo'g'imsimon efedra	<i>Efedra equisetina</i>	Х.хвоцевидная	X. equisetoides
34	Tog' terak	<i>Populus usbekistanica</i>	Топол узбекистанский	Mountain poplar
35	Oqterak	<i>Populus alba</i>	Топол белый	White poplar
36	Qoratol	<i>Salix australior</i>	Ива южная	Black Willow
37	Echkitol	<i>Salix songorica</i>	Ива джунгарская	Goat Willow
38	Qush jiyda	<i>Elaeagnus angustifolia</i>	Лох узколистный	Russian olive
39	Sharq jiydasi	<i>Elaeagnus orientalis</i>	Лох восточный	East oleaster
40	Jumrutsimon chakanda	<i>Hippophae rhamnoides</i>	Облипеха крушиновидная	Sea buckthorn
Biodiversity of cultivated plants				
41	Qrim qarag'ayi	<i>Pinus pallasiana</i>	Сосна крымская	Crimean pine
42	Eldor qarag'ayi	<i>Pinus eldarica</i>	Сосна элдарская	Eldor pine
43	Tyan – Shan qoraqarag'ayi	<i>Pinus Shrenkiana</i>	Ел тяншанская	Tian Shan black pine
44	Tikanli qoraqarag'ay	<i>Pinus pungens</i>	Ел колючая	Picea pungens 'Snow Kiss
45	Oq qarag'ay	<i>Abies</i>	Пихта	White pine
46	Semenov oqqarag'ayi	<i>Abies Semenovii</i>	Пихта Семенова	White-Pine Semenova
47	Tilog'och	<i>Larix</i>	Лиственница	Larch
48	Doim yashil sekvoyya	<i>Sequoia sempervirens</i>	Секвойя вечнозелёная	Sequoia evergreen
49	Glibtostrobussimon metasekvoyya	<i>Metasequoia glibtostroboides</i>	Метасеквойя глиптостробоидная	Metasequoia glyptostroboides

50	Virgin archasi	<i>Juniperus virginiana</i>	Можжевельник виргинский	Juniperus virginiana
51	Kazak archasi	<i>Juniperus sabina</i>	Можжевельник казацкий	Juniper of Kazak
52	Uzun bandli archa	<i>Juniperus oblonga</i>	Можжевельник длинноветвистый	Juniper long branched
53	G'arb tuyyasi	<i>Thuja occidentalis</i>	Туя западная	Western camel
54	Sharq biotasi	<i>Biota orientalis</i>	Биота восточная	Oriental biota
55	Mevali zarnab	<i>Taxus baccata</i>	Тисс ягодный	Yew berry
56	Ginkgo biloba	<i>Ginkgo biloba</i>	Гинкго двулопастный	Ginkgo biloba
57	Yirik gulli magnoliya	<i>Magnolia grandiflora</i>	Магнолия крупноцветковая	Large-flowered Magnolia
58	Lola daraxti	<i>Liriodendron tulipifera</i>	Тюльпанное дерево	Tulip tree
59	Tunberg zirki	<i>Berberis Thunbergii</i>	Барбарис тунберга	Thunberg Barberry
60	G'arb chinori	<i>Platanus occidentalis</i>	Платан западный	Western maple
61	Zarangbargli chinor	<i>Platanus acerifolia</i>	Платан клёнолистный	Platanus acerifolia
62	Doimyashil shamshod	<i>Buxus sempervirens</i>	С.вечнозелёный	Evergreen Shamshod
63	Oddiy eman	<i>Quercus robur</i>	Дуб летный	Simple Oak
64	Kashtanbargli eman	<i>Quercus castaneafolia</i>	Дуб каштанолистный	Chestnut oak
65	Oq qayin	<i>Betula pendula</i>	Берёза повислая	White Birch
66	Maydabargli jo'ka	<i>Tilia cordata</i>	Липа мелколистная	Small-leaved linden
67	Yirik bargli jo'ka	<i>Tilia grandifolia</i>	Липа крупнолистная	Large-leaved linden
68	Ipak akatsiyasi	<i>Albizia julibrissin</i>	Албиция ленкоранская	Silk acacia
69	Kanada bagryannigi	<i>Cersis canadensis</i>	Багряник канадский	Canadian redbud
70	Yapon soforasi	<i>Sophora japonica</i>	Софора японский	Japanese sophora
71	Dala zarangi	<i>Acer campestre</i>	Клён полевой	Field maple
72	Shumtolbargli zarang	<i>Acer negunda</i>	Клён ясенелистный	Broadleaf maple
73	O'tkir bargli zarang	<i>Acer platanoides</i>	Клён остролистный	Sharp-leaved maple
74	Soxta kashtan	<i>Aesculus</i>	Конский каштан	False chestnut

75	Pissarda olxo'risi	<i>Prunus cerasifera</i> Ehrh.	Слива писсарди	Pissardi plum
76	Pensilvaniya shumtoli	<i>Fraxinus pennsylvanica</i>	Ясен пенсильванский	Pennsylvania Ash
77	Oddiy devorgul	<i>Ligustum vulgare</i>	Бирючина обыкновенный	Simple wall-flower
78	Marjondaraxt	<i>Sambucus</i>	Бузина	Necklace tree
79	Qorsimon mevali buta	<i>Symphoricarpus albus</i>	Снежноягодник белый	White snowberry

The species naturally distributed or cultivated in the mountainous and foothill zones of the Ohangaron River basin include nearly 100 species—primarily trees and shrubs introduced from Europe and Central Asia, as well as several vine species.

Naturally growing trees and shrubs contribute to stabilizing the ecological balance of the region in forest melioration. For example, they prevent soil erosion, and when trees grow densely, underground water evaporation decreases, which leads to an increase in spring water flow. Furthermore, during winter and spring, trees retain a portion of precipitation, reducing surface runoff and promoting 40–60% (depending on soil type) water infiltration into the soil.

Cultivated plants also help to improve the ecosystem and microclimate of the region from a sanitary and hygienic perspective. Additionally, ornamental trees and shrubs planted for landscaping residential areas provide open-air recreational opportunities. One hectare of forest can produce enough oxygen for 200 people per hour. It would not be an exaggeration to call such plantations "natural air conditioners" for society.

Figure 3. Cultivated introduced broad-leaved larix trees in a forest nursery

Therefore, based on each region's geographic location and climatic conditions, it is important to preserve natural flora and ensure biodiversity by cultivating resilient and ornamental

plants adapted to the local climate. Purposeful use of these plants for greening urban and rural areas, increasing tourism, and establishing parks and alleys for cultural recreation is among the pressing issues of today.

REFERENCES

1. Nurxodjaev A.K. Qiziqarli geologiya. Bosh muharrir B.F.Islamov. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi geologiya va mineral resurslar davlat qo‘mitasi. Geologiya fanlari universiteti. - Toshkent, “Lesson Press” MChJ nashriyoti, 2022. - 185 bet.
2. Рамазонов О., Юсупбеков О. //ТУПРОҚШУНОСЛИК ВА ДЕХҚОНЧИЛИК. Тошкент — 2003, 76 бет.
3. Turdiyev S.A., Tilovova G.A. Toshkent voxasi tog‘ va tog‘ oldi florasining bioxilma xilligi. “BARQAROR O‘RMONCHILIK” IV XALQARO ILMIY-TEXNIK ANJUMAN IV INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE FORESTRY – 2024-YIL 1-2-NOYABR.
4. Тожиев У., Намазов Х., Нафетдинов Ш., Умаров К. Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси давлат илмий нашриёти. 2004. - 76 бет
5. [https://n.ziyouz.com/books/kollej_va_otm_darsliklari/geografiya/O'zbekiston%20tabiiy%20geografiyasi.%202-qism%20\(I.Hasanov,%20P.G'ulomov\).pdf](https://n.ziyouz.com/books/kollej_va_otm_darsliklari/geografiya/O'zbekiston%20tabiiy%20geografiyasi.%202-qism%20(I.Hasanov,%20P.G'ulomov).pdf)
6. https://api.scienceweb.uz/storage/publication_files/2979/14521/6555c5a4760bb_%D0%A2%D1%83%D0%BF%D0%BB%D0%B0%D0%BC.%20%D0%98%D0%BA%D0%BB%D0%B8%D0%BC%20%D1%83%D0%B7%D0%B3%D0%B0%D1%80%D0%B8%D1%88%D0%B8%20-2023.pdf